

A comparative study to assess the assertive behavior and impart the knowledge of assertiveness among male and female college students in selected college of Bilaspur Chhattisgarh

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15291487>

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Abstract

Assertiveness is an adaptive style of communication in which individuals express their feelings and needs directly, while maintaining respect for others. A lack of assertiveness may contribute to depression and anxiety, whereas maladaptive approaches to assertiveness may manifest as aggression (American Psychological Association). Men and women tend to differ in their assertiveness in some ways, but there is a wide range of assertiveness among both men and women, and assertiveness is not a trait that is limited to one gender. Gender differences in assertiveness are not only found in speech, but also in behaviour. Research has found that, overall; men tend to show more assertive behaviours than women, such as stating an opinion or refusing an unreasonable request.

Keywords: Assertive behavior, assess, knowledge, college students

Introduction

Assertiveness or social boldness is the ability to be legitimate and honest in terms of one's rights, interests, and beliefs, while not denying or ignoring the rights of others (Rathus, 1973) ^[1]. Rakos (1991) ^[2] divides assertiveness into two categories, positive and negative. Positive assertiveness includes behaviors like expressing positive feelings, giving and receiving compliments along with admitting to personal mistakes and shortcomings whereas negative assertiveness includes expressing unpopular opinions, refusing reasonable requests and requesting behavior changes in other people. Eason (2018) ^[3] highlighted other benefits of being assertive including increased self-confidence, stronger ability to overcome negative thoughts, better goal setting, and becoming better at listening. Social anxiety and stress were also found to decrease with increase in assertiveness (Pourjali & Zarnaghash, 2010) ^[4]. People who unable to assert themselves are more prone to have low sensitivity towards criticism, low self-esteem, higher anxiety and extreme passivity (Marano, 2004) ^[5]. A strong correlation was found between assertive behaviour and self-esteem of

Indian adolescents (Shanmagan & Kathy-ayini, 2017). It is extremely important for young adults to practice assertiveness in order to identify their strengths, build confidence and solidify their identity (Çok & Kara-man, 2008) ^[6].

Assertiveness as a social skill is a construct which has a number of different dimensions, including the ability to express oneself without anxiety or aggression in different situations (M. Bouvard, *et al.*, 1999) ^[7]. Assertiveness is about effective communication and this does not just mean choosing the right words to say in a given situation. Tone of voice, intonation, volume, facial expression, gesture and body language all play a part in the message you are sending to the other person, and unless all parts of the equation match, you will be sending a garbled message (Bishop, 2000) ^[8]. According to Galassi and Galassi (1978) ^[9], "assertion is the direct and appropriate communication of a person's needs, wants and opinions without punishing, threatening, putting down others, and doing this without fear during the process."

Review of Literature

1. Literature related to assertiveness

Soma Chakraborty, Aparna Ray, Smriti Kana Mani (2020) ^[10] conducted a comparative survey study to assess and compare assertiveness, self-esteem and leadership potentiality between 64 (sixty-four) 3rd year B.Sc. nursing students of College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata; Government College of Nursing, S.S.K.M. Hospital, Kolkata and 60 (sixty) General college students of Brahmananda Keshab Chandra College, Bonhooghly, Kolkata, West Bengal. Non-probability purposive sampling technique was adopted. The tool consisted of socio-demographic profile, standardized tool for assessment of assertiveness and self-esteem and 30 item structured questionnaire for assessment of leadership potentiality. The study findings reveal that assertiveness (mean difference -0.74), self-esteem (mean difference-3.47) and leadership potentiality (mean difference»7.19) among general college students are higher than those of nursing college students. The results also indicate that assertiveness is positively correlated with self-esteem [t df (58)=2.00; $p<0.05$] and leadership potentiality [t df (58)=2.00; $p<0.05$] among general college students ^[10].

Thenmozhi. P, D. Divya Bharathy (2019) ^[11] study was conducted with the aim to relate the assertiveness with academic performance. Non-experimental descriptive study was chosen to conduct a study in selected arts and Science College with 60 samples. The tools used for the study was Assertiveness scale and Academic performance scale. Out of 60 samples, 4(6.7%) were situationally assertive, 26(43.3%) were somewhat assertive, 30(50%) were assertive. In assessing the academic performance 23(38.3%) had good performance, 34(56.7%) had moderate performance, and 3(5%) had poor performance. The study finding also shows that there is a positive relationship between the level of assertiveness and academic performance. The present study concluded that there is a lack of assertiveness among students which directly or indirectly affect their academic performance of the students. It is necessary that every school or college should provide the assertive training program to face the challenges and cope up with the current situation in the world ^[11].

Hakeem. S Sujatha. N (2016) ^[12] conducted a study to assess the level of assertiveness among B.Sc. Nursing students studying in Chettinad College of Nursing, Kelambakkam, Kanchipuram district, Tamil Nadu, India. In this study the researcher assessed the level of assertiveness by distributing the demographic variables proforma and assertiveness inventory schedule to the samples. The samples were instructed to fill the inventory schedule and the schedule was collected from the samples by the researcher. The study results stated that majority (40%) of the samples belongs to the age group of 18-19 years, whereas only (10%) were in the age group of 16-17 years. A large proportion (63%) of the samples belongs to the gender of female, (36%) were in the gender of male. Most (60%) of the samples belongs to the religion of Hindu, whereas only (7%) were in the religion of Muslim. Almost (83%) of the samples belongs to the board of study during schooling of state board, whereas only (7%) were in the board of schooling of CBSE. Among the samples (37%) of the parents have primary education, whereas only (10%) were in the parents were illiterate.

Majority (40%) of the samples belongs to the family monthly income of Rs 10000 above, whereas only (17%) were in the family monthly income of Rs < 5000 It also reveals that majority (53%) of the samples belongs to the type of personality of dependent, shy, reserve, asocial, introvert, whereas only (47%) were in the type of personality of independent, open, social, extrovert ^[12].

2. Literature related to assertiveness with reference to gender

C. Prince Samuel and Dr V. Chandrasekharan (2018) ^[13] conducted a study to assess the assertiveness of college students in relation to the background variables such as Gender, Medium of Instruction and Type of family. The sample consist of 70 undergraduate students selected from Coimbatore and Tirupur Districts of Tamil Nadu for this study. Self-constructive assertiveness questionnaire was used in this study for data collection. The collected data were subjected to suitable statistical analysis and scores of the sample were computed. The results indicates that Female students had better Assertiveness than male students, English medium students had better assertiveness than Tamil medium students and Science students had better assertiveness than Arts students which offers implications to take up and direct special efforts to improve the Assertiveness of Male students, Tamil Medium students and Arts students to strengthen their communication skills and personality development ^[13].

W. M. Parray, Sanjay Kumar (2016) ^[14] conducted a study to assess the assertiveness among Undergraduate Students of the University. The sample of the study comprised of 100 adolescents both urban and rural (50 males and 50 females). They belong to age range of 16 to 22 years and were undergraduate students of following courses- Bachelor of Arts, Science and Commerce. The present study revealed that there is no significant difference among students with respect to their gender, residence and stream of study. But it is confirmed that there is significant difference among students in their assertiveness score. During the analysis it was found that among 100 (students) respondents, 11 were 'Situationally non-assertive', 35 'Somewhat assertive', 45 'Assertive', and 9 were 'probably aggressive'. Based on the above findings it is clearly indicated that there is lack of assertiveness among students. So, for an adolescent to develop into a complete adult it is highly imperative to teach him some coping strategies and one of the most important and useful skill is assertiveness. By inculcating this skill an adolescent will be able to express both positive and negative feelings honestly and straightforwardly, without anxiety or intimidation. As a conclusion an assertiveness training could be beneficial for developing adolescents' assertive behaviors and this enhancing program could be incorporated into everyday curriculum in schools, colleges and universities. The study may helpful for the students to understand the level and importance of assertiveness ^[14].

3. Literature related to assertiveness training programme

Saradha. I, Dr. Sasikala. T, Dr. Baby Rathinasabapathy (2022) ^[15] conducted a study to evaluate the effectiveness of Assertiveness Training Programme (ATP) to impart assertive behaviour among adolescents. A pre-experimental

with one group pre and post-test research design was used quantitatively. A Simple random sampling technique was used to select the subjects. The Data was collected from 60 adolescents by using the "Rathus Assertiveness Schedule" to assess the assertive behavior. The same Modified "Rathus Assertiveness Schedule" was used to assess the post-test level of assertive behavior among adolescents. The results revealed that there was a significant difference in the pre-and post-test level of assertive behavior among adolescents. The overall 't' value obtained was 12.14 and $p = 0.001$ where $p < 0.001$ which means that the assertiveness training Program (ATP) has shown significant changes in improving assertive behavior in adolescents. There is an association between assertive behaviors of adolescents with their selected demographic variable for age significant at 0.005 level. The study concluded that the assertiveness training program is an important aspect in imparting assertive behavior so that it helps the adolescent to develop decision making, coping skills to face various challenges in our society [15].

Saba Asif, Dr. Zaqia Bano, Uzma Sarwar (2021) [16] conducted a study aimed to determine the effectiveness of assertive training as an intervention to develop and improve social emotional competences among adolescents in Sialkot, Pakistan. The quasi- experimental design (pre-test-post-test with control test) was used. Data was collected by using simple random sampling used. Data was collected by using simple random sampling technique. A sample of 40 adolescents was obtained and was further divided into two groups: experimental group was comprised of 20 participants (girls 10, boys 10) and control group with the same number. A demographic sheet and Social- Emotional Competence Questionnaire (SECQ) were used for data collection. The experimental group attended assertive training while the control group did not receive treatment. Paired sample t-test showed statistically significant difference in means of overall score of SEC before and after treatment ($t = -15.50, p = .000$). Moreover, the pre-post difference on the level of dimensions of social emotional competence was highly significant (pairwise t-tests; all $p < .05$) in the intervention group except on the dimension of decision making with ($t = 1.67, p = .110$). The findings of the experiment concluded that assertive training significantly improved the overall social emotional competencies among adolescents [16].

Research Methodology

A quantitative approach, Non-experimental comparative research design is used in this study. In the present study assertive behavior is the research variable. Prior permission was obtained from the Principal of the college. After obtaining student’s consent, 6 samples (3 male and 3 female) who fulfilled the criteria were selected by purposive sampling method. The pre-test was done with the help of Modified Rathus assertive scale and multiple-choice questionnaires. After taking responses the investigator provide structure teaching on assertiveness. The post-test was done with the help of Modified Rathus assertive scale and multiple-choice questionnaires. The duration of the pilot study was 1 week. After the pilot study the tool was found

to practicable and acceptable. The main study was done on 02/07/2024 in the C.M. Dubey Post Graduate College Bilaspur (C.G.). 60 samples were taken for the main data collection, 30 male and 30 female students.

Data Analysis

Distribution of subjects according to socio demographic variables by using frequency and percentage

Table 1: Distribution of Subject According to Age

Age in year	Males		Females	
	N	%	N	%
18 years	10	33.33	11	36.67
19 years	5	16.67	5	16.67
20 years	9	30	8	26.67
21 years	6	20	6	20
Total	30	100	30	100

Table 1: depicts that 33.33% male and 36.67% female college students belong to age group of 18 years, 16.67% male and 16.67% female college students belong to age group of 19 years, 30% male and 26.67% female college students belong to age group of 20 years and 20% male and 20% female college students belong to age group of 21 years.

Table 2: Distribution of Subject According to Stream of study

Stream of study	Males		Females	
	N	%	N	%
Arts	25	83.33	23	76.67
Commerce	4	13.33	6	20
Science	1	3.34	1	3.34
Total	30	100	30	100

Table 2: reveals that 83.33% male and 76.67% female students having arts stream, 13.33% male and 20% female students having commerce stream, 3.34% male and 3.34% female students having science stream.

Table 3: Distribution of Subject According to residence

Residence	Males		Females	
	N	%	N	%
Rural	21	70	19	63.33
Urban	9	30	11	36.67
Total	30	100	30	100

Table 3: reveals that 70% male and 63.33% female students belong to rural area, 30% male and 36.67% female students belong to urban area.

Table 4: Distribution of Subject According to medium

Medium	Males		Females	
	N	%	N	%
Hindi	20	66.67	16	53.33
English	10	33.33	14	46.67
Total	30	100	30	100

Table 4: reveals that 66.67% male and 53.33% female students belong to Hindi medium, 33% male and 46.67% female students belong to English medium.

Table 5: Distribution of Subject According to Family income

5. Family income	Males		Females	
	N	%	N	%
<Rs5000/-	4	13.33	3	10
Rs 5001-10000/-	10	33.33	12	40
Rs10001-20000/-	7	23.34	7	23.33
>Rs20001/-	9	30	8	26.67
Total	30	100	30	100

Table 5: reveals that 13.33% male and 10% female students belong to <5000/- family income, 33.33% male and 40% female students belong to 5001-10000/- family income, 23.34% male and 23.33% female students belong to 10001-20000 family income, 30% male and 26.67% female students belong to >20001 family income.

Table 6: Distribution of Subject According to Religion

Religion	Males		Females	
	N	%	N	%
Hindu	26	86.67	26	86.67
Muslim	2	6.67	2	6.67
Christian	2	6.67	2	6.67
Sikh		0		0
Total	30	100	30	100

Table 6: reveals that 86.67% male and 86.67% female students are Hindu, 6.67% male and 6.67% female students are Muslim, 6.67% male and 6.67% female students are Christian, 0% male and 0% female students are Sikh.

Table 7: Distribution of Subject According to Type of family

Type of family	Males		Females	
	N	%	N	%
Nuclear family	16	53.33	20	66.67
Joint family	13	43.34	9	30
Extended family	0	0	0	0
Single parenting	1	3.33	1	3.33
Total	30	100	30	100

Table 7: reveals that 53.33% male and 66.67% female students belong to nuclear family, 43.34% male and 30% female students belong to joint family, no male and female students belong to extended family, 3.33% male and 3.33% female students belong to single parenting.

Table 10: Association between assertive behavior in male students with their selected socio-demographic variables.

Age group	Assertive behavior in Males			Total	DF/Critical value	Chi square value	Inference $p < 0.05$
	Nonassertive (-90 to -30)	Assertive (-30 to +30)	Aggressive (+30 to +90)				
18 years	5(50%)	5(50%)		10(100%)	3/7.82	8.75	Significance
19 years	0(0%)	5(100%)		5(100%)			
20 years	5(55.56%)	4(44.44%)		9(100%)			
21 years	0(0%)	6(100%)		6(100%)			
2. Stream of study							
Arts	8(32%)	17(68%)		25(100%)	2/5.99	1.02	Not Significant
Commerce	2(50%)	2(50%)		4(100%)			
Science	0(0%)	1(100%)		1(100%)			

Table 8: Distribution of Subject According to Occupation of father

Occupation of father	Males		Females	
	N	%	N	%
Farmer	17	56.67	17	56.67
Businessman	5	16.67	5	16.67
Doctor	1	3.33	1	3.33
Engineer	0	0	0	0
Other	7	23.33	7	23.33
Total	30	100	30	100

Table 8: reveals that the father of 56.67% male and 56.67% female students belong to farmer, father of 16.67% male and 16.67% female students belong to businessman, father of 3.33% male and 3.33% female students belong to doctor, father of 0% male and 0% female students belong to engineer.

Table 9: Assess the assertive behavior and compare between the male and female college students of selected college Bilaspur Chhattisgarh

Study Group	Assertive behavior			Total
	Nonassertive (-90 to -30)	Assertive (-30 to +30)	Aggressive (+30 to +90)	
Males	10(33.33%)	20(66.67%)		30(100%)
Females	14(46.67%)	16(53.33%)		30(100%)

Fig 1: Bar diagram depicting distribution of subject according to Assertive behavior

Table 10 & Figure 1: reveals that 33.33% male and 46.67% female students come under non-assertive behavior, 66.67% male and 53.33% female students come under assertive behavior and no male and female students come under aggressive behavior.

Association between assertive behavior with their selected socio-demographic variables

3. Residence							
Rural	7(33.33%)	14(66.67%)		21(100%)	1/3.84	4.00	Significance
Urban	3(33.33%)	6(66.67%)		9(100%)			
4. Medium							
Hindi	6(30%)	14(70%)		20(100%)	1/3.84	0.30	Not Significant
English	4(40%)	6(60%)		10(100%)			
5. Family income per month							
<Rs 5000/-	1(25%)	3(75%)		4(100%)	3/7.82	0.39	Not Significant
Rs 5000-10000/-	4(40%)	6(60%)		10(100%)			
Rs 10000-20000/-	2(28.57%)	5(71.43%)		7(100%)			
>Rs 20000/-	3(33.33%)	6(66.67%)		9(100%)			
6. Religion							
Hindu	8(30.77%)	18(69.23%)		26(100%)	2/5.99	5.07	Not Significant
Muslim	0(0%)	2(100%)		2(100%)			
Christian	2(100%)	0(0%)		2(100%)			
Sikh	8(30.77%)	18(69.23%)		26(100%)			
7. Type of family							
Nuclear family	7(43.75%)	9(56.25%)		16(100%)	3/7.82	4.66	Not Significant
Joint family	2(15.38%)	11(84.62%)		13(100%)			
Extended family							
Single parenting	1(100%)	0(0%)		1(100%)			
8. Occupation of father							
Farmer	7(41.18%)	10(58.82%)		17(100%)	3/7.82	2.21	Not Significant
Businessman	2(40%)	3(60%)		5(100%)			
Doctor	0(0%)	1(100%)		1(100%)			
Engineer							
Other	1(14.29%)	6(85.71%)		7(100%)			

Table No. 10: Above Table shows the association between the assertive behavior level among males with selected socio-demographic variables such as Age in year, Stream of study, Residence, Medium, Family income by using a non-parametric X² test.

On applying the chi-square test demographic variable “Age group” and “residence” was significantly associated with the assertive behavior among males. The X² value of “Age group” was 8.57 greater than the table value (7.82) and X² value of “residence” were 4.0 greater than the table value (3.84) at level of significance $p < 0.05$. Hence there will be a significant association between assertive behaviors of male

students with selected socio-demographic variable (age and residence) of college students is accepted.

Association between the assertive behavior level among males and other selected socio-demographic variables such as Stream of study (X² =1.02), medium (X² =0.30), Family income (X² =0.39), Religion (X² =5.07), Occupation of father (X² =2.21) were found to be statistically not significant at level of $p > 0.05$. Hence there is no significant association between selected socio-demographics like Stream of study, medium, Family income, religion with the assertive behavior level among males is accepted.

Table 11: Association between assertive behavior in female students with their selected socio-demographic variables.

Age group	Assertive behavior in Females			Total	DF/Critical value	Chi square value	Inference $p < 0.05$
	Nonassertive (-90 to -30)	Assertive (-30 to +30)	Aggressive (+30 to +90)				
18 years	4(36.36%)	7(63.64%)		11(100%)	3/7.82	9.09	Significance
19 years	1(20%)	4(80%)		5(100%)			
20 years	3(37.5%)	5(62.5%)		8(100%)			
21 years	6(100%)	0(0%)		6(100%)			
2. Stream of study							
Arts	12(52.17%)	11(47.83%)		23(100%)	2/5.99	1.58	Not Significant
Commerce	2(33.33%)	4(66.67%)		6(100%)			
Science	0(0%)	1(100%)		1(100%)			
3. Residence							
Rural	11(57.89%)	8(42.11%)		19(100%)	1/3.84	2.62	Not Significant
Urban	3(27.27%)	8(72.73%)		11(100%)			
4. Medium							
Hindi	7(43.75%)	9(56.25%)		16(100%)	1/3.84	0.12	Not Significant
English	7(50%)	7(50%)		14(100%)			

5. Family income per month							
<Rs 5000/-	1(33.33%)	2(66.67%)		3(100%)	3/7.82	0.34	Not Significant
Rs 5000-10000/-	6(50%)	6(50%)		12(100%)			
Rs 10000-20000/-	3(42.86%)	4(57.14%)		7(100%)			
>Rs 20000/-	4(50%)	4(50%)		8(100%)			
6. Religion							
Hindu	12(46.15%)	14(53.85%)		26(100%)	2/5.99	0.02	Not Significant
Muslim	1(50%)	1(50%)		2(100%)			
Christian	1(50%)	1(50%)		2(100%)			
Sikh							
7. Type of family							
Nuclear family	13(65%)	7(35%)	0(0%)	20(100%)	3/7.82	8.15	Significance
Joint family	1(11.11%)	8(88.89%)	0(0%)	9(100%)			
Extended family							
Single parenting	0(0%)	1(100%)	0(0%)	1(100%)			
8. Occupation of father							
Farmer	11(64.71%)	6(35.29%)		17(100%)	3/7.82	6.13	Not Significant
Businessman	2(40%)	3(60%)		5(100%)			
Doctor	0(0%)	1(100%)		1(100%)			
Engineer							
Other	1(14.29%)	6(85.71%)		7(100%)			

Table 11: Above Table shows the association between the assertive behavior level among females with selected socio-demographic variables such as Age in year, Stream of study, Residence, Medium, Family income by using a non-parametric X² test.

On applying the chi-square test demographic variable “age” and “Type of family” was significantly associated with the assertive behavior among females. The X² value of “age” and Type of family was 9.9 and 8.14 greater than the table value (5.99 and 7.82) at 2 & 3 degree of freedom. Hence there will be a significant association between assertive behaviors of female students with selected socio-demographic variable (age and Type of family) of college students is accepted.

Association between the assertive behavior level among females and other selected socio-demographic variables such as Stream of study (X² =1.58), Residence (X² =2.62), Medium (X² =0.12), Family income (X² =0.34), were found to be statistically not significant. Hence there is no significant association between selected socio-demographics like Stream of study, Residence, Medium, Family income with the assertive behavior level among females is rejected.

Conclusion

The findings of the study concluded that there is not significant association exist between gender and Assertive behavior of college students of selected college Bilaspur Chhattisgarh.

References

- Rathus SA. A 30-item schedule for assessing assertive behaviour. *Behav Ther.* 1973;4(3):398–406.
- Rakos RF. *Assertive behaviour: Theory, research, and training.* 1991.
- Eason A. *The importance of being assertive: Why you’ll benefit from being assertive.* 2018.
- Pourjali F, Zarnaghash M. Relationships between assertiveness and the power of saying no with mental

- health among undergraduate students. *Procedia Soc Behav Sci.* 2010;9:137–141.
- Marano HS. Assertive, not aggressive [Internet]. *Psychology Today.* 2004 [cited 2025 Apr 27]. Available from: <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/articles/200402/a-assertive-not-aggressive>
- Cok F, Karaman NG. *Taking risk in adolescent.* Oxford: Symposium Books; c2008.
- Bouvard M, Arrindell WA, Guerin J, Bouchard C, Rion AC, Ducottet E, *et al.* Psychometric appraisal of the Scale for Interpersonal Behavior (SIB) in France. *Behav Res Ther.* 1999;37:741–762.
- Bishop S. *Develop your assertiveness.* New Delhi: Replica Press Private Limited; c2010.
- Galassi MD, Galassi JP. Assertion: A critical review. *Psychother Theory Res Pract.* 1978;46:537–554.
- Chakraborty S, Ray A, Mani SK. A comparative study regarding assertiveness, self-esteem and leadership potentiality between students of selected nursing and general college in West Bengal. *Int J Nurs Midwif Res.* 2020;7(3):4–11.
- Thenmozhi P, Divya Bharathy D. Relationship between the level of assertiveness and academic performance among arts and science college students. *Asian J Nurs Educ Res.* 2019;9(3):293–296.
- Hakeem S, Sujatha N, Manjula TR. A descriptive study to assess the level of assertiveness among B.Sc. Nursing students studying in Chettinad College of Nursing, Kelambakkam, Kanchipuram district, Tamil Nadu, India. *Glob J Res.* 2016
- Samuel CP, Chandrasekharan V. A study on assertiveness of college students. *Int J Creat Res Thoughts.* 2018;389.
- Parray W, Kumar S. Assertiveness among undergraduate students of the university. 2016;4:2348–5396.
- Saradha I, Sasikala T, Rathinasabapathy B. A study to

- evaluate the effectiveness of assertiveness training programme (ATP) to impart assertive behaviour among adolescents. *J Posit Sch Psychol.* 2022;6(8):1389–1397.
16. Asif S, Bano Z, Sarwar U. Effectiveness of assertive training in developing social-emotional competencies among adolescents. *Pak Soc Sci Rev.* 2021;5(4):58–70.

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